

INFLUENCE OF SELECTED SCHOOL VARIABLES ON PRINCIPAL'S JOB PERFORMANCE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

The sustainable development of the school system is related to the job performance of school principals, whose crucial roles are vital in the day-to-day administration of secondary schools. This study investigated the job performance of secondary school principals and some selected demographic and institutional variables namely gender, ownership of school, school location, school size and principals' years of experience. The design of the study was the descriptive survey. The population consisted of public and private secondary school principals. The sampling technique was the stratified sampling procedure employed to ensure equal representation of the strata of the population and a simple of three hundred and thirteen were selected from the population. The instrument for the study was the questionnaire with a reliability coefficient of 72 obtained by the use of spearman Brown product moment formula. The data was collected and analyzed using frequency, percentages and Pearson products moment correlation testy for significance of 0.5. the job performance of school principles of good and very good levels. There was significant relationship between job performance levels of school principals and the variables of ownership of school public and private schools, school location of urban and rural and school size of small and large. Also there was significant relationship between job performance levels and school principals gender and years of experience. Thus, it is recommended that state ministry of education should organise seminars, and workshops for all principals irrespective of school ownership and location to enhance their job performance. Also the appointment to the office of school principal should be not only be based on seniority or longevity of service, but it should include professional qualification to make the position respected and competence-based. This will contribute to performance improvement of school principals.

Key word: School principals; Job performance; gender; ownership of school; school location and size; principals' years of experience.

Introduction

The job performance of principals is crucial in the sustainable development of the school system. The school principal is the overall administrator which is in charge of administrative and academic duties in the school. The responsibilities of principals span through academic leadership, personnel and financial Management; and including the implementation of government policies. The principals act as link between educational authorities of the government and school communities, therefore the principals influence the teaching and learning, teacher Moral and student achievements. With regard to the complexity of their roles, and understanding the factors that affect principals job performance, it is pertinent to note that the job performance of school principals is crucial for building viable education system towards the achievement of the national goals of education.

As the chief executive of the school the principal have the responsibilities of creating conducive environment for teaching and learning, managing student and teachers, allocating resources and pursuing academic excellence in sharing the duties of the school (Dunu 2023& Adeyemi and Okemakinde 2023).

Also knowing that certain variables could influence principal's job performance, this has emerged as a crucial area of educational research and policy interest.

Several variables have been identified as influencing the effectiveness of secondary school principals job performance in Nigeria. These include demographic variables/factors of gender, principals years of administrative experience, ownership of the school (public or private); school location (urban and rural) and school size (large and small). Gender may influence the leadership style. As observed by Okeke *et al.*, (2023) that gender as a subject continues to be a subject of interest in relationship to perception of competence which may differ along gender lines. This could not be surprising in Nigerian society where cultural and social political structures often influence leadership roles. Therefore, investigating the rule of gender in job performance is necessary in accessing job performance of principals of schools.

The personal professional experience is often sighted as a variable in determining the effectiveness of leaders. It could be assumed that longer years of service could add to deeper knowledge on job leading to stronger administrative skills. But Ajayi and Yusuf, (2024) posited that the correlation between experience and job performance is not always linear, as experience may also bring competency into the job performance. It should be noted that length of time on administrative position often leads to complacency and resistance to change and innovation.

Ownership of schools; both public and private school have principals in leadership position. While public school principals operates school in line with the government bureaucratic directives facing challenges or inadequacies in finance, infrastructure and personnel, the private school principals contend which competition against each other for public attention. As opined by Oyetunji and Arikewuyo (2022) public schools face challenges such as inadequate funding and political interference, while their counterparts in private school experience more autonomy.

School location of urban and rural environment could be a variable that could affect principal's job performance. Urban schools have advantage of resources in personal and facilities while rural schools are in deficiency both of staff and facilities (Ezechi *et al* 2023).

School size may have impact on the workload, delegation and student teacher ratio. Similarly the size of school attract the scope of principal administrative duties. The principal of a large school will require complexity in administrative duties than a small School.

Though there have been researchers on the individual variables, limited research has examined their collective and interactive impact on principal's job performance. This study seeks to fill the gap by exploring how gender, ownership of school, school location, school size and principals experience relate to their job performance. The findings aim to inform policy makers, educational administrators and leadership development programs contributing to efforts to enhance school effectiveness and achieve sustainable educational development goals in Nigeria.

Statement of problem

The position of the secondary school principal and the importance of principal job performance is crucial to the sources and achievement of educational goals at the secondary level of education. The school principal job performance is a critical factor in determining the effectiveness of schools. Secondary school administrators play a vital in shaping the educational experiences of students and managing school resources. The leadership role of staff and supervising instruction are also his duties, but it is necessary to point out that the factors influencing principal job performance are complex and multifaceted.

There is a lack of understanding about factors that influence principals job performance. Researchers previous studies have investigated the principal job performance and his personal variables such as leadership style, job, related stress, teachers moral and motivation. But there is the need to examine the relationship between principal job performance and other variables specifically the relationship between principal job performance and variables such as gender, school ownership (public and private) school location (urban and rural) school size and principal's job experience which could influence the principal's job performance.

Without a clear understanding of the factors that influence principals job performance like different characteristics such as Urban and rural, or public and private which many required different types of support

and resources to ensure that principals can perform effectively. Also lack of training and professional growth could affect the principal experience on the job performance. Hence this study examines the relationship of school principal job performance in relation to selected variables of gender, ownership of school, school location, school size and principal's experience.

Research objective

The objective of this research is to investigate the relationship between secondary school principals job performance and selected variables of gender, principal's experience, ownership of school, school location and school size.

The study specifically sought to:

- determine the relationship between principal job performance and gender
- assess the impact of principal's experience on job performance
- examine the effect of school location (urban vs rural) on principal's job performance
- compare the job performance of principals in public and private schools
- investigate the relationship between school size and principals job performance

Research questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study

1. What are the levels of job performance among secondary school principals
2. To what extent do the variables of selected variables of gender, years of experience, ownership of school location and school size influence secondary school principals?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between job performance of male and female principals
2. There is no significant relationship between job performance level among less experience and experienced school principals.
3. There is no significant relationship between job performance level among public and private secondary school principals.
4. There is no significant relationship between job performance of urban and rural school principals
5. There is no significant relationship between job performance of principals of small and large schools.

Review of related literature

The position, roles and responsibilities of the principal is very crucial in achieving and shaping educational goals in the education system. Also the job performance of principal are necessary for the sustainable development of education in schools. It is pertinent to mention that the job performance of principals are influenced by factors which include gender, school location, size and ownership and the experience of the principal.

Gender bias of school principals and job performance:

Gender bias has always been on issue in educational research at all levels. Researchers have tried to point out the influence of gender in studies. School principals are both males and females qualifications and have attained the position of a school principal as a result of qualification and length of service in the teaching profession.

Nwonkwo (2023) in his studies found there was significant difference in the administrative competencies between male and female principals due to management behaviors. Obiekwe *et al* (2023) in their research reported that male principals were perceived to perform better in maintaining discipline and managing conflicts, both genders were effective in the area of supervision of instruction.

In another gender study of principal by Eileen *et al.*, (2020) on male and female principal School climate and job satisfaction the research reviewed that there was no significant gender based differences among the principals in their job performance.

School ownership and job performance

In Nigeria today schools' are owned by government and private proprietors and organizations such as churches, industries, companies and so on. They have been studies on diverse issues relating to ownership of schools (public and private) to the extent that the Nigerian Association for Educational Administrative and Planning (NAEAP) Journal of vol.5. No 2, July 2005 was devoted to special issue on "public and private school decoratory in Nigeria Education System.

Yanki and safia (2016) in their research findings reported that private schools in the rural and urban areas were not affected by school location but by the strong personalities and insufficient skills due to lack of professional school management training. In kwara state Olaifa (2023) reported that the job performance of private school was moderate.

School location and Job Performance

Schools are located both in the urban and rural areas of the country. The influence of school location on the job performance of school principles has been revealed by some studies. In emotional intelligence, school location and job performance in public secondary schools in Delta State, Ekedama (2023) concluded that school location significantly attract the performance of the teachers. While Hirchi & Smith (2020) highlighted the role of school location in sampling and performance of school administrators, Solem & Vaughan (2023) were of the opinion that other factors like teaching experience and availability of resources in school could contribute to positive jobs performance. But Titus *et al* (2016) posited that schools located in places or proximity to commercial areas could pose distractions and have adverse effect on the school principal's job performance. Oyeleye and Ayodele (2023) reported that school location affected principals administrative performance which was influenced by the disparities in resources and support between the Urban and rural schools thereby creating differences in the job performance of urban and rural principals. In the research work of Ekedama *et al* (2023) their findings indicates that school location directly affected teachers' job performance.

School Size and Job Performance

A school with a small population will be easier to manage than the one with a large population. Studies on school size as a variable are limited. But it must be mentioned that larger schools in comparison with small schools may have more complex administrative challenges which could affect the job performance of the school principal.

Principal's experience and job performance

Experience of the school principal would affect his administrative effectiveness. An experienced principal who had been on the job will be a better administrator than a experience graduate principal fresh from the University.

Dunu (2023) and Obikwe *et al* (2023) findings indicated that experienced principals are better equipped to Foster effective teaching environment in schools. Obikwe *et al* (2023) stated that experienced principals demonstrated better competencies in supervision, personnel management and communication which were significantly related to teachers dedication to duty.

Through considerable literatures exist on variable affecting principal's job performance, integrative studies examining multiple factors simultaneously are limited. This study is examining multiple variables of gender, ownership of school, school location and size and principals' experience on job performance

Methodology

The design adopted for this study was a descriptive survey which involves a collection of quantitative data from a large number of respondents to describe the existing conditions and relationships between principal's job performance and selected variables, including gender, school ownership, location, size and years of experience.

The population of the study comprised all principals of public and private secondary schools across the 25 local government areas of the State. A stratified random sampling technique was used to ensure that participants were drawn proportionally for the different categories of schools based on ownership, (public slash private) location (rural/urban) and school size (small/medium/lage) using a comprehensive list of school obtained from the Ministry of Basic and Secondary School, Asaba, Delta State (deltastatemobse.net). A total of 313 principals were selected from across the States, 164 public school principals and 149 private school principals. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "principals job performance and demographic variables questionnaire (PGPDVQ)". The questionnaire consisted of two sections

Section A: demographic data including gender, years of experience, school ownership, school location and school size

Section B: items measuring principal's job performance across key domains: administrative duties, leadership skill, school management of staff and students. This was rated on four points likert scale of poor performance 1 point, fair performance 2 points, good performance 3 points and very good performance four points.

The set of questionnaire was validated to establish face, content and construct validity by expert in the Faculty of Education in University of Delta, Agbor. All their useful suggestion and corrections where considered in producing the instruments. To ensure reliability, 30 principals from non-sampled school were used and using the spearman Brown products moment formula, the instrument yielded a reliability coefficient of 72, indicating a high level of reliability.

Questionnaires were administered by the researchers and trained research assistants to ensure high response return rate. The data was analyzed by the use of frequency, sample percentage and Pearson product moment correlation. They were use to examine the relationship between the selected variables of gender, school ownership, school location, school size and years of experience and job performance.

Data presentation

Demographic data

Table 1: Respondents personal and information about respondent School

	Personal Information	No	Percentage
Gender	Male	194	62
	Female	119	38
Total		313	100
Experience Of Principal	Less Experienced	118	37.7
	Experienced	195	62.3
Total		313	100
School Location	Urban	190	60.7
	Rural	123	39.3
Total		313	100
School Size	Small	223	71.3
	Large	90	28.7
Total		313	1000

Table 1 gives a breakdown of school principals information with respect to gender, years of experience, ownership of school, school location, and school size. The Table showed 194 (62%) where male and 119 (38%) where female. Experienced school principals where 195 (62.3%) while 118 (37.7%) wireless experienced information on school shows respondents in information on ownership of schools, school location of school size. Public school were 100 (51.1%) while private school were 153 (48.9%). Schools located in urban areas were 190 (60.7%) while rural school were 123 (39.3%). Small schools were 223 (71.3%) (which comprised of small and moderate size school with a population of 501-1000) and these large schools were 90 (28.7%) which comprised of large and very large school with population of 1,000 and above.

Research question one; What are the levels of job performance of secondary school principals?

Table 2: Frequency and percentage of secondary school principals job performance levels.

Job performance	Frequency	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Poor	23	7.3	7.3
Fair	71	22.7	30.0
Good	108	34.5	64.5
Very good	111	35.5	100
	313	100	

Presented on Table 2 are the frequencies and percentage of secondary school principals' job performance quality. In the Table, poor performance had lowest frequency of 23 (7.3%) 71 principals add fair job performance which represented 22.7%, 108 (34.5%) were of good performance while the highest frequency of 111 (35.5%) had very good performance.

Research Question 2; What are the job performance of secondary school principals and selected variables?

Table 3: Mean scores of job performance of secondary school principals and selected variables.

Variables		X	SD
Ownership of school	Public	3.36	.30366
	Private	2.59	.90706
Gender of Principal	Male	2.95	.95109
	Female	3.03	.91501
Location of school	Urban	2.83	.90250
	Rural	3.18	.86174
School size	Small	3.07	.92996
	Large	2.80	.92469
Experience of school principal	Less-experienced	3.02	.93702
	Experienced	2.76	.80147

Table 3 shows the mean ranges of job performance of secondary school principals with selected variables of ownership of school, gender of principal, location of school, school size and principal's experience. The variables had means scores above the cut-off Mean of 2.5 and therefore shows that the job performance of secondary school principals in connection with all the variables are acceptable as being above average. Revealing good job performance by secondary school principals.

Testing for hypotheses

Hypotheses One; There is no significant relationship between job performance levels among public and private secondary school principals.

Table 4; Relationship between job performance levels among public and private school principal school .

Variables	X	SD	Calculated r value	critical r value
Public	3.36	.80366	.874	.113
Private	2.59	.90706		

P < 05; df = 311

Table 4 shows that mean for the job performance of public and private secondary school principals are 3.36 and 2.59 respectively. The calculated r values is .874.

This shows that there is a significant relationship between job performance levels among public and private secondary school principals. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 2; There is no significant relationship between job performance of male and female secondary school principals.

Table 5: Relationship between job performance levels of male and female secondary school principals.

Variables	X	SD	calculated R value	critical value
Male	2.95	.95109	.859	.113
Female	3.03	.91561		

P < 0.5; df = 311

Table 5: Shows the Pearson product moments correlation between job performance level. Of male and female secondary school principals. The mean score for male school principals is 2.95 and the mean score for female school principals is 3.03. The calculated r value is .859 and the critical r value is .113. The calculated value is greater than the critical r value. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between job performance among male and female secondary school principal.

Hypothesis three: There is no significant relationship between job performance levels of urban and rural secondary school principals.

Table 6 Relationship between job performance among urban and rural secondary school principals .

Variables	X	SD	Calculated R value	Critical r value
Urban	2.83	.90250	.830	.113
Rural	3.18	.86174		

P < .05; df = 311

Table 6 shows the Pearson product moments correlation between job performance levels of urban and rural secondary school principals. The mean of the urban and rural secondary school principals are 2.84 and 3.18 respectively. The calculated r value is .830. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the job performance levels of urban and rural secondary school principals.

Hypothesis four: There is no significant relationship between job performance levels of school principals of small and large secondary schools. **Table 7** relationship between job performance of secondary school principals of small and large schools.

Variables	X	SD	Calculated value	R	Critical r value
Small school	3.07	.92996	.856		.113
Large school	2.80	.92469			

P < 0.5; df = 311

Table 7 shows Pearson product moments correlation between job performance levels of secondary school principals of small and large schools. The mean scores for small and large schools are 3.07 and 2.80 respectively. The calculate r value is 8:56 and the critical r value is 113. Therefore there is a significant relationship between job performance level of school principals of small and large schools.

Hypothesis five: there is no significant relationship between the job performance levels among less experienced and experienced School principals.

Table 8 Relationship between job performance levels of less experienced and experienced secondary school principals

Variables	X	SD	Calculated value	R	Critical r value
Less expensive	3.02	.93702	.867		.113
Experienced	2.76	.80147			

P < 0.5; df = 311

Table 8 shows Pearson product moments correlation between job performance of less experienced and experienced secondary school principals. The mean scores of less experienced and experienced secondary school principals are 3.02 and 2.76 respectively.

The calculated r value is 859 and the critical r value is .113. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

There is a significant relationship between job performance levels of less experience and experienced secondary school principal .

Discussion of Findings

Research question 1 determined the job performance levels of secondary school principal . This study revealed that 70% of the school principals are good and very good quality job performance while only 7.3% of the school principals had poor performance with 22.7% having a fair job performance.

The findings of principal's job performance and selected variables of gender, ownership of school, location and size of school and experience of school principals revealed that the principals had means scores above the benchmark of 2.50, indicating high job performance of school principals despite the disparities of gender, ownership of school location and size with the years of experience among them. The principals performed equally well and employed similar leadership skills in carrying out their duties. This is agreement with the study of Watson & Vita-Agundu (2023) who reported principal male and principal female performed highly in their administrative duties in the management of senior secondary schools, in Rivers state of Nigeria

School ownership and Principals job performance in secondary schools.

The findings of this study showed that the public schools principals had higher performance in relation to the private schools; meaning that there was a significant relationship between the job performance of public and private school principals. This study is in line with Olaifa (2023) who reported that private schools had a moderate job performance when compensation strategies was linked with job performance. This highlighted the influence of school management practices on job performance.

This finding was not in agreement with Olaifa (2023). In her studies, private school principals performed better than public school principals. A higher performance by public school principals could have resulted due to the current trends of events in the state during the period of research. In recent time, the state ministry of education has been laying emphasis on improving secondary school administration in order to curb examination malpractice and students mass failure in external examinations.

It is pertinent to mention that the public secondary schools have more qualified and experienced principals. Most of the public school principals have been on the job for a long time before rising to the position of school principal. They also have added advantage of having subordinates; the vice principals who assists them in the day to day administration of the school. Also the change in the status and social image of public school principals had made public school principals to improve their professional capacity, therefore rededicated to their professional duties, resulting in better job performance.

Gender and principals job performance: The findings on gender (male/female) school principals and job performance revealed that there was a significant relationship between the job performance levels of principals in relation with their gender. The findings is supported by the study of Nwonkwo (2023) who reported that there was significant differences in the administrative of school between male and female principals due to management behaviours. But the findings is not in agreement with Obiekwe *et al* (2023). in their studies, male principals were perceived to perform better than female principals in maintaining discipline and managing conflicts., but Eileen *et al* (2020) in their study reported that there was no significant gender based differences among the principals in their job performance, contrary to the findings of this study.

School principals, male and female, have attained their position or office due to their academic qualification and number of years in service. Both face the same administrative routine and pressures in the schools. Nowadays both male and female school principals are blazing up to face the challenges and carry out their administrative duties as professionals to improve performance

School location and principals job performance.

The study showed a significant relationship between the job performance levels of both urban and rural principals. This study was supported by the research Findings of Oyeleye & Ayodele (2023) Ekedana *et al* (2023). But the researchers like Salem & Vaughan (2023) and Titus *et al* (2016) reported that other factors of teaching experiences and availability of resources; proximity to commercial areas posed more distractions and have adverse effects on school principals job performance. Although, one would have expected that there are distinctions between urban and rural schools in terms of numbers of teachers, unfair distribution of resources and relationships with school communities. It is still relevant to note that the urban and rural school principals perform similar duties and responsibilities in their duty posts.

Also, worthy of note is that teaching as a profession involves transfer from one location to another. School principals are usually transferred from urban to rural and from rural to urban. A school principal who has worked in both locations will perform moderately anywhere at a given period of time, in course of his/her administrative duties at any of the locations.

School size and principals job performance

This study revealed there is a significant relationship between large and small school principals job performance. The size of a school may not reflect on the job performance of school principals. As earlier mentioned, principals position is not static as principals serve in small or large schools at one time or the other. From one school to the other, he acquires experience, which could aid performance in any of the school size he finds himself. Through there are studies specifically on school size, but it should be noted that the size of school may not have implications on the job performance of school principals, since principals are usually transferred from one school to another, either a large or small school.

Principals experience and job performance

The research findings revealed there was a significant relationship between principals experiences and job performance. The findings of the study of Dunu (2023) and Obiekwe *et al* (2023) agree with the findings, noting that experienced principals demonstrated better competencies in administrative skills. These studies suggest that experienced principals are better equipped to perform supervision, personnel management and communication areas in administrative duties.

Conclusion

This study on the investigation into the relationship between secondary school principals job performance and selected variables of gender, ownership of school, school location, school size and principals experience revealed that the principals experience had a high job performance level.

The principals' job performance as it correlates to ownership of school of public and private was instructive as performance had significant relationships, though private school principals could have been influenced in administrative efficiency due to greater anatomy, resource and facilities availability. While public school principals face constraints in areas of limited resources and bureaucratic bottleneck administrative hurdles. Gender of school principals demonstrated that performance was tied to professional equity not the male or female domains. School location and size significantly related to principals job performance, since Urban principals could benefit in staffing and acquiring more facilities, as it goes for larger schools while Rural and small school principals had some disadvantages posing some challenges. The principals experience correlated positively, suggesting years of experience leads to effectiveness.

Recommendations.

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended as follows:

- The state ministry of education should organize seminars, workshops, and conferences for all principals irrespective of ownership of schools and location. This will go a long way in training them in act of school administration and exchange of ideas. They should also be encouraged and given opportunities to attend other senior and top management courses with their counterparts in management positions in other ministries. This will not only expose them but give them positive feelings of the importance of their position and enhance their job performance.
- Appointment to the office of a principal have been based on seniority or longevity of service. It is still necessary that appointment to such office, should entail strict land down criteria to include professional qualification to make the position respected and competency based. This will contribute to performance improvement.
- School principals should be transferred on regular basis to both urban and rural, large and small schools to have experience in different locations and sizes of schools. This could boost performance since change sometimes have positive effects.
- The state government could establish a system of reward for school principals, this could be merit reward, best school academic achievement, long service reward, personality reward and others, these could enhance performance of school principals.
- Resource limitation and bureaucratic constraints on public school principals which poses challenges on public school principals in their performance of their administrative duties should be addressed. Such disparities between public and private school environments should be minimized to encourage positive performances, by distribution of facilities to public schools.

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